

A Cognitive Preference Profiles in Engineering Students: A Cluster Analysis of Learning Tendencies and Cerebral Hemispheric Orientation

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ARTICLE INFO	ABSTRACT
Published Online: 23 December 2025	School dropout in the first year of engineering faculties is a current topic. Possible solutions depend on many variables like the students' learning style, the teaching methods, learning material, etc; Therefore, solutions can only be proposed adapted to the particularities of the study group (students learning style, teacher methods, material, etc). This study analyzes the cognitive preference profiles in a sample of engineering students. In this respect, a correlation between the learning style and the cerebral hemispheric orientation for each student in sample has been done using the “Preference learning style questionnaire” and the “Cerebral hemispheric preference” questionnaire, both created by Ricki Linksman (1999). Furthermore, cluster analyses were used to determine the student's cognitive profiles based on which pedagogical recommendations and teaching methods for engineering education are made.
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I. INTRODUCTION

Every student, person or learner experiences educational process and understands information in a way that is uniquely their own. These differences appear from a combination of psychophysiological factors or personal approaches to reasoning and problem-solving [1]. These aspects are very important not only in how students assimilate new material, but also in how they integrate the abstract concepts in real life. Because students do not think, perceive, or process in the same way, a uniform educational model does not have better performances in training future engineering for examples. Modern education requires individualization and differentiation of instructional approaches [2]. In other words, each student has a learning profile and style which are helpful in creating new teaching methods. Today, there are also machine learning techniques used to identify them [3]. When pedagogical methods are adapted to these profiles, learning becomes more meaningful, more efficient, and more sustainable, because the learning process is designed in such a way that all learners have support: those who are visually, those who prefer structured verbal explanations, or those who learn best through doing [1,4].

This perspective was successfully applied to engineering education, where students from technical faculties have to understand and integrate many abstract mathematical concepts, spatial-visual representations, algorithmic thinking, laboratory experimentation, or different design tasks [5].

Students differ not only in learning styles: visual, auditory, tactile, or kinesthetic [6], but also in the cognitive orientation through which they analyze or synthesize information [7]. These tendencies, often referred to as cognitive preferences, include both perceptual learning styles and broader hemispheric processing orientations [8,9].

The first one reflects favored modes of interaction with content. Visual students tend to learn fast from diagrams, spatial representations, and symbolic structures; auditory-oriented learners respond well to verbal explanation and sequential narration; tactile and kinesthetic learners excel in manipulation, hands-on experimentation, and active movement [10,11]. Hemispheric processing orientation describes how learners analyze and organize information. Although cognitive functions are distributed across both hemispheres, the research suggests that each person uses most one of them. Learners with a left-oriented hemisphere typically prefer structured, sequential, and detail-focused reasoning, relying on rules, symbolic representations, and stepwise procedures. Those with a right-oriented tendency respond more to holistic, visual-spatial, and intuitive approaches, organizing information through patterns, images, and global conceptual frames. Many students exhibit mixed profiles, flexibly shifting between analytical and holistic strategies depending on task demands, while a smaller number has an integrated profile that combines both modes simultaneously, allowing them to coordinate detailed analysis with higher-level conceptual understanding [8,9,12]. These

heterogeneous processing tendencies play a particularly important role in engineering education, where students must alternate between mathematical formalism, spatial visualization, system-level reasoning, and hands-on experimentation.

The students performance and cognitive profiles were investigated based on learning styles, individual [1,4,6,7,9,13] or grouped in clusters [14–17], but none of these researches did not take into account the hemispheric orientation. Students rarely function according to a single dominant mode and as a result, there is increasing interest in building integrated learner profiles that combine several behavioral indicators into a single representation of learning variability.

Despite their relevance, learning styles and cerebral hemispheric preference have rarely been examined together in engineering education. This correlation is favors the development of accelerated learning competencies [18]. Existing work relies heavily on frequency comparisons and chi-square tests. Cluster analysis is a powerful technique widely used in psychology and learning analytics.

Starting from the idea that school dropout is mostly due to the learning difficulties that students encounter in the first year, this paper proposes a teaching method based on Cognitive Preference Profiles. The main contributions of the present paper are:

Identify learning styles and cerebral hemispheric preference for 91 students from a technical faculty. We used two instruments proposed by [18].

Analyze the relationship between those aforementioned factors that influence learning process: we test whether they are statistically associated or whether they operate independently.

Identify integrated cognitive profiles: using cluster analysis, we examine whether students naturally group into distinct profiles that combine learning styles and hemispheric orientations into cognitive patterns.

Based on those clusters, we propose some pedagogical recommendations and teaching methods for engineering education.

Introduce a novel computational indicator: the Cognitive Profile Index (CPI). One of the key original contributions of this paper is the proposed of a numerical index that integrates perceptual and hemispheric tendencies into a single continuous score ranging from -1 to +1. This provides an engineering-friendly, quantitative representation of each student's cognitive profile or allows numerical comparison between clusters.

II. THEORETICAL BACKGROUND

A. Learning Styles

Learning styles are a current topic in the recent research in the fields of education, psychology and neuroscience. The field of learning styles and methods encompasses not only

many research studies in the field, but lately also a series of commercial activities addressed to the public audience. In [19,20] a review can be consulted of all these materials and fields that address this concept of learning style. There are mentioned both aspects related to the impressive number of studies carried out in this field, as well as the textbooks and not least the websites that facilitate learning style testing and determination activities.

In scientific literature there are perhaps as many definitions of learning style as there are theories and models that have been developed. A comprehensive definition that declares learning styles as being the “way in which each learner begins to concentrate on, process, absorb, and retain new and difficult information” [21-23]. [24] highlights that this concept can lead to different ways in which theorists understand this concept, so that their methods for assessment and observations may be different. This is the reason why there are so many different definitions and models for the learning style assessment in scientific literature.

Specialized studies conducted in recent decades have shown that learning styles represent a combination of natural and acquired habits. We receive information about the outside world through all five human senses but depending on the stimuli to which our brain was exposed, interconnections were created between nerve cells. The more stimuli we receive, the more interconnections - learning patterns are formed. The more often the brain is exposed to stimuli of the same type, the simpler, faster and more automatic the corresponding learning pattern becomes and thus, the best learning style is formed [25]. If the learning material is presented in such a manner that facilitates its reception through the appropriate sense - the preferred learning style - then a greater efficiency of the learning process can be ensured.

One categorization of learning style is related to the four human senses through which we receive information from the surrounding world. Therefore, according to [25-26] there are four learning styles: visual, auditory, tactile and kinesthetic. Visual learners receive information through the visual sense; therefore, they are receptive to displayed materials and demonstrations of new information. Auditory learn by reading aloud or discussing and processing thoughts out loud. Tactile learners receive information through the sense of touch, so they learn easily if the new information is presented in such a way that allows them to use their hands, fingers, their perceptions sense. Kinesthetic learners learn easily being in motion: by activating their motor muscles, by engaging in movement activities or exploiting new concepts. Even if there is a preferable cognitive way of receiving information, it must be mentioned that there are people who use two, three or all of four styles to learn.

B. Cerebral Hemisphere

Lately research in the neuroscience field has been progressed enormously and today offers an understanding of

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how the brain works. Human brain is divided into two hemispheres. Generally, people use both cerebral hemispheres, but the new information processing and its storage is done predominantly by using one of these hemispheres, demonstrating a cerebral hemispheric preference. When we predominantly use certain neural pathways, we are practically strengthening those neural pathways, transforming it into the preferable cerebral hemisphere. We become more efficient in using that hemisphere and so; by finding it simpler and more comfortable to use it, we will use it more frequently.

Ideally, people should be able to use both cerebral hemispheres appropriately for the task at hand. But to be able to do this, a certain amount of training is necessary. Scientific discoveries in this field are relatively recent, and the academic environment is trying to maximize the efficiency of these discoveries. In the meantime, however, the cerebral hemisphere development is an aspect that it is left to chance - people are developing their cerebral hemispheres purely randomly - depending on the stimuli frequency they are subjected to in childhood.

The correlation between learning style and the preferred cerebral hemisphere was called by R. Linksman with the suggestive term “the super link for learning”. The learning style and the cerebral hemispheres work together. Learning style is associated with different ways of receiving information from the world and transmitting information from the senses to the brain. Cerebral hemispheric preference deals with how we work with information – how we process it and how we store it, once it reaches to the brain.

Sensory data received by sight, hearing, touch or through the muscles of the body can be channeled to the left or to the right cerebral hemisphere. They process and store the information in different ways as follows: symbolic/sensory or step-by-step/simultaneously. The left cerebral hemisphere processes data symbolically, in the form of numbers, letters, words and abstract ideas, while the right hemisphere does it in a sensory way, perceiving the world through the senses, without words. The left cerebral hemisphere is the one that deals with language. The right hemisphere processes data without language. It perceives visual, auditory, gustatory, olfactory, tactile, movement, music, human voice sounds, and nature without assigning labels to them. In other words, the right cerebral hemisphere perceives life as a movie without dialogue. The left hemisphere stores information step by step. It absorbs information in a linear order, successively, one at a time. It has difficulty perceiving the big picture at once. In contrast, the right hemisphere stores information globally, simultaneously – it sees the big picture at once. It has difficulty rehearsing information step by step, if it does not get the big picture.

Although the two hemispheres have different tasks, the humans merge them and use both hemispheres. The aspect that is being studied in recent research is that when we have

to understand and learn new concepts, we tend to use our preferred cerebral hemisphere - the one with which we find it easiest/comfortable/handy to process the new information. Therefore, if we would receive data through our preferred hemisphere, it would be easier and more natural to accelerate the learning process. This is the aspect this paper aims to enhance in building new teaching methods and pedagogical proposals.

III. MATERIALS AND METHODS

All paragraphs must be indented as well as justified, i.e. both left-justified and right-justified.

A. Participants (Size 10 & Bold)

The entire document should be in Times New Roman or Times font. Other font types may be used if needed for special purposes. Type 3 fonts should not be used.

To identify individual learning style, the cerebral hemisphere preference and the correlation between them, we applied a specific set of questionnaires to a sample of 91 technical engineering students, from different specializations of Faculty of Automation, Computers, Electrical and Electronic Engineering: Electrical Engineering, Electronics and Telecommunications and Electrical Engineering and Computers. Demographic distribution, presented in Table 1 and Figure 1, shows that 85.7% of participants were male, while 14.3% were female. The study specialization distribution (Figure 2) shows that IE engineering students were preponderant in the student sample.

Table 1. Demographic distribution

Gender		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Female	13	14,3	14,3	14,3
	Male	78	85,7	85,7	100,0
	Total	91	100,0	100,0	

Figure 1. Gender distribution

Figure 2. Studies specialization distribution

B. Instruments

This study utilizes a descriptive quantitative research design to determine the correlation between learning styles and the dominant cerebral hemisphere in the sense of determining what is called in the specialized literature the “super link for learning”. In this perspective we used the “Preference learning style questionnaire” and the “Cerebral hemispheric preference” questionnaire, both created by Ricki Linksman (1999). These two questionnaires were centralized and the statistical analysis have been done with IBM SPSS Statistic.

C. Procedure

The questionnaires were completed successively, within the same time frame. Completion of the questionnaires was completely voluntary. Students were informed that questionnaire completion is anonymous, and the research data will be strictly confidential. Also, they have been informed about the fact that the research results will be used exclusively for academic purposes and that they can quit the questionnaires completion whenever they want to - if they changed their mind regarding their participation in this research.

The students in sample completed the two questionnaires, performed the score calculation by themselves and after that they have completed a Google form with their obtained results. This allows the researchers to centralize the research results without any external implication in the process

D. Statistical Analysis

The collected data using the two Ricki Linksman questionnaires were centralized and statistically analyzed using IBM SPSS Statistic. In the first part of the article, a statistical analysis of possible correlations between the learning style and, respectively, the cerebral hemisphere and the variables that could possibly influence them (gender, specialization, etc) was carried out. For the analysis of the correlation between the Learning Style and the Cerebral Hemisphere, the Crosstabulation and Chi-Square Tests have been used.

Based on the analyses of the correlation tendencies results, a Two Step Cluster analyses have been done to determine the Cognitive Profile Index.

E. Cognitive Profile Index

To integrate the information obtained from the learning styles questionnaire and the hemispheric processing orientation instrument into a single, comparable metric, we propose a Cognitive Profile Index (CPI). This index transforms two categorical, qualitatively different constructs into a numerical variable that reflects each student’s overall cognitive profile. This approach enables a more compact representation of learner variability, supports quantitative comparisons between clusters, and provides an engineering-friendly metric.

The CPI was constructed in two stages. First, learning styles were coded along an ordinal perceptual continuum ranging from predominantly visual to predominantly kinesthetics. The four categories (Visual, Auditory, Tactile, Kinesthetics) were mapped to values 1–4 and then linearly normalized to the interval [-1, +1] using a symmetric transformation, centered at 2.5 and divided by 1.5 (which is (4-1)/2), resulting in a symmetric and interpretable score. This score has the following interpretation: negative values indicating a tendency toward visual and sequential information processing, and positive values reflecting a preference for tactile or kinesthetics’, action-oriented modes of engagement. The proposed formula for this normalization is:

$$S_{norm} = \frac{Style - 2.5}{1.5}, \tag{1}$$

The S_{norm} values for the mentioned styles are:

Table 2. S_{norm} values

Style	Values	S_{norm} values
Visual	1	-1
Auditory	2	-0.3
Tactile	3	+0.3
Kinesthetic	4	+1

Second, cerebral hemispheric preferences were encoded in the same mode as styles, on a scale ranging from -1 to +1. Based on established behavioral descriptors, left-oriented profiles were assigned a value of -1, right-oriented profiles +1, while mixed and integrated profiles received intermediate values (-0.3 and +0.3, respectively) to reflect blended or balanced orientation. The value in this case has the same relation as S_{norm} , noted with H.

The final CPI score for each student was computed as the arithmetic means of the normalized score S_{norm} and the hemispheric orientation code:

$$CPI = \frac{S_{norm} + H}{2} \tag{2}$$

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The resulting index ranges from -1 (visual–left/mixed preference) to +1 (tactile/kinesthetic–right/integrated orientation), with values near zero indicating balanced profiles. This index was used to examine distributional differences between the clusters identified in SPSS, to visualize cognitive patterns, and to quantify the degree of separation between groups.

F. Teaching Strategy Proposal

The objective of present research is to analyze the super link for learning/cognitive profile for a sample of students in engineering faculty. Once it has been determined, the objective is to propose, develop and implement a teaching strategy to help students to learn easily and implicitly decrease the school dropout rate in the first year of study. The teaching strategy proposal will be founded on the present research results and conclusions.

IV. RESULTS

A. Learning tendencies

No more than three levels of headings should be used. All headings must be in 10pt font. Every word in a heading must be capitalized except for short minor words as listed in Section III-B.

The analysis was done in IBM SPSS Statistic. The results reflecting the learning tendencies, in Figure 3, revealed noticeable differences between technical specialization.

Figure 3. Learning styles tendencies on technical domains

Table 3 (Style/Domain Crosstabulation) expose the correlation between the learning style and study specialization. It can be observed that visual learners were most frequently found in Electrical Engineering (50%), whereas tactile and kinesthetic learners were more prevalent in Electronics (42.9% and 52.2% respectively). In contrast, students in Electrical Engineering and Computer Science showed lower representation of tactile (14.3%) and kinesthetic (8.7%) preferences. Auditory learners were evenly distributed across all specializations (33.3% in each group). These descriptive results suggest that learning style patterns vary across academic programs at a surface level.

Table 3. Style Domain Crosstabulation

	Count	Domain			Total
		IETTI	IE	IEC	
Visual	36	8	18	10	36
	% within Style	22,2%	50,0%	27,8%	100,0%
Auditory	18	6	6	6	18
	% within Style	33,3%	33,3%	33,3%	100,0%
Tactile	14	6	6	2	14
	% within Style	42,9%	42,9%	14,3%	100,0%
Kinesthetic	23	12	9	2	23
	% within Style	52,2%	39,1%	8,7%	100,0%
Total	91	32	39	20	91
	% within Style	35,2%	42,9%	22,0%	100,0%

The style/domain crosstabulation reveals not a significant statistical relationship between specialization and learning style for this sample, as proven also by chi-square analysis. Considering the technical specifics of the faculty, it was expected that there would not be a significant difference between learning styles preferred by specializations, but that the visual learning style would be the preferred one. There could be a significant statistical difference between the learning style but reported to the specific of the faculty (not the specialization in the same faculty profile)– this will make the subject of future research.

The Chi-Square test examining the association between learning style and specialization (Table 4) was not statistically significant, $\chi^2(6) = 8.57, p = .199$. Fisher’s Exact Test confirmed the absence of a significant association ($p = .196$).

Table 4. Chi-Square Tests for Stile/Domain

Chi-Square Tests				
	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)	Exact Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	8,574 ^a	6	,199	,203
Likelihood Ratio	9,004	6	,173	,203
Fisher's Exact Test	8,523			,196
N of Valid Cases	91			

a. 3 cells (25,0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 3,08.

Figure 4. Learning styles tendencies

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The distribution of learning style preferences per global (Figure 4) indicated a dominant inclination toward visual (almost 40%). Kinesthetic learning styles were the second most prevalent ($\approx 25\%$), suggesting that a considerable proportion of students benefit from movement, interaction, and experiential engagement during learning tasks. Auditory learners represented approximately 20% of the sample, while tactile learners accounted for the lowest percentage ($\approx 15\%$). These results highlight a heterogeneous cognitive profile within the student population, with a particularly strong visual preference consistent with patterns frequently reported in technical and educational engineering contexts.

B. Cerebral Hemisphere tendencies

Figure 5. Cerebral Hemispheric tendencies on technical domain

Figure 6. Distribution of cerebral hemispheric tendencies per quantity

Analysis of hemispheric preference (Figure 6) showed a relatively balanced distribution between left (about 35%) and mixed dominance (33%), followed by right hemispheric preference (30%). Only a negligible percent is for an integrated hemispheric profile (2-3%), indicating that simultaneous bilateral processing is uncommon among the participants. These results suggest that most students tend to rely predominantly on either sequential-analytical (left) or flexible/multimodal (mixed) processing styles, with a notable proportion showing right-hemispheric reliance associated with global and intuitive reasoning patterns.

Table 5. Hemisphere Domain Crosstabulation

		Domain			Total
		IEITI	IE	IEC	
Hemisphere Left	Count	10	14	8	32
	% within Hemisphere	31,3%	43,8%	25,0%	100,0%
	Right	Count	10	11	6
	% within Hemisphere	37,0%	40,7%	22,2%	100,0%
Integrated	Count	0	0	2	2
	% within Hemisphere	0,0%	0,0%	100,0%	100,0%
Mixed	Count	12	14	4	30
	% within Hemisphere	40,0%	46,7%	13,3%	100,0%
Total	Count	32	39	20	91
	% within Hemisphere	35,2%	42,9%	22,0%	100,0%

The distribution of hemispheric dominance across specializations showed no statistically significant association, $\chi^2(9) = 15.07$, $p = .089$. Left-, right-, and mixed-hemisphere respondents appeared across all academic programs in comparable proportions, indicating that hemispheric preference is not linked to specialization. Although integrated hemisphere responses were recorded only within the Electrical Engineering and Computer Science group, the frequency was too small ($n = 2$) to support interpretation.

Table 6 Chi-Square Tests for Hemisphere/Domain

Chi-Square Tests		Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)	Exact Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square		8,755 ^a	6	,188	,182
Likelihood Ratio		7,873	6	,248	,293
Fisher's Exact Test		6,120			,372
N of Valid Cases		91			

a. 3 cells (25,0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is ,44.

The Chi-Square test assessing the association between hemispheric dominance and specialization (Table 6) was not statistically significant, $\chi^2(6) = 8.76$, $p = .188$, with Fisher's Exact Test confirming the absence of an association ($p = .372$).

C. Learning Style - Cerebral Hemispheric correlated tendencies

Figure 7. Learning Style - Cerebral Hemispheric correlated tendencies

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Table 7 Learning Style/ Cerebral Hemispheric Crosstabulation

		Hemisphere				Total	
		Left	Right	Integrated	Mixed		
Style	Visual	Count	16	4	2	14	36
		% within Style	44,4%	11,1%	5,6%	38,9%	100,0%
Auditory	Count	6	6	0	6	18	
		% within Style	33,3%	33,3%	0,0%	33,3%	100,0%
Tactile	Count	4	8	0	2	14	
		% within Style	28,6%	57,1%	0,0%	14,3%	100,0%
Kinesthetic	Count	6	9	0	8	23	
		% within Style	26,1%	39,1%	0,0%	34,8%	100,0%
Total	Count	32	27	2	30	91	
		% within Style	35,2%	29,7%	2,2%	33,0%	100,0%

The cross-classification between learning styles and hemispheric dominance (Table 7) revealed distinct distribution patterns. Visual learners were mainly associated with left-hemispheric dominance (16) and mixed dominance (14), while only a small number aligned with right-hemispheric processing (4) or integrated profiles (2). Auditory learners showed a relatively balanced distribution across left, right and mixed hemispheric preferences (6). Tactile learners were most frequently linked to right-hemispheric dominance (8), with fewer cases falling into left or mixed categories. Kinesthetic learners demonstrated a stronger association with right dominance (9) and mixed profiles (8), while fewer aligned with left-hemispheric patterns.

Table 8 Chi-Square Tests for Learning Style/ Cerebral Hemispheric

	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	15,071 ^a	9	,089
Likelihood Ratio	16,596	9	,055
Linear-by-Linear Association	,017	1	,897
N of Valid Cases	91		

a. 7 cells (43,8%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is ,31.

A chi-square test was conducted to examine whether learning style was associated with hemispheric dominance (Table 8). The association did not reach statistical significance, $\chi^2(9, N = 91) = 15.07, p = .089$, suggesting that the distribution of learning styles across hemispheric categories does not differ from what would be expected by chance. Although descriptive patterns indicated tendencies such as visual learners aligning more frequently with left or

mixed dominance and kinesthetic learners showing stronger right-hemisphere representation, these differences were not statistically supported.

Questioning if there is any determination between the student’s learning style and the student’s cerebral dominant hemisphere, we made a symmetric analysis.

Table 9 Symmetric measures

Symmetric Measures		Value	Asymptotic Standard Error ^a	Approximate T ^b	Significance
Interval by Interval	Pearson's R	-,014	,106	-,129	,898 ^c
Ordinal by Ordinal	Spearman Correlation	,032	,109	,305	,761 ^c
N of Valid Cases		91			

- a. Not assuming the null hypothesis.
- b. Using the asymptotic standard error assuming the null hypothesis.
- c. Based on normal approximation.

The symmetric measures analysis, presented in Table 9, showed no linear association between learning style and hemispheric dominance. Pearson’s correlation was negligible and non-significant ($r = -0.014, p = .898$), and Spearman’s rank-order correlation likewise indicated no significant monotonic relationship ($\rho = .032, p = .761$). These results confirm that learning style does not correlate linearly or ordinally with hemispheric dominance in the sample ($N = 91$).

D. Correlation between Gender, Learning Style and Cerebral Hemisphere

To see if there is any correlation between gender and the cerebral hemisphere preference or between gender and the learning style we proceed to make the following analysis.

1. Gender - Cerebral Hemisphere

Figure 8. Gender - Cerebral Hemisphere correlated tendencies

The grouped bar chart (Figure 8) illustrates the distribution of hemispheric dominance across gender categories. Female participants showed a higher proportion of right-hemispheric dominance, followed by left dominance, with very few cases categorized as mixed and none classified

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as integrated. In contrast, male participants demonstrated a different pattern, with mixed dominance being the most frequent, followed by left-hemispheric and right-hemispheric profiles. Integrated dominance appeared only among males and at very low frequency.

Table 10. Gender/Cerebral Hemisphere Crosstabulation

		Hemisphere				Total	
		Left	Right	Integrated	Mixed		
Gender	Female	Count	5	6	0	2	13
		% within Gender	38,5%	46,2%	0,0%	15,4%	100,0%
Male	Count	27	21	2	28	78	
	% within Gender	34,6%	26,9%	2,6%	35,9%	100,0%	
Total	Count	32	27	2	30	91	
	% within Gender	35,2%	29,7%	2,2%	33,0%	100,0%	

The cross-tabulation between gender and hemispheric dominance in Table 10 showed different distribution patterns for male and female students. Among female participants (n=13), right-hemispheric dominance was most frequent (46.2%), followed by left dominance (38.5%), while mixed dominance was less common (15.4%) and no cases showed integrated hemispheric processing. In contrast, male students (n=78) exhibited a different pattern, with mixed hemispheric dominance being the most prevalent (35.9%), followed by left dominance (34.6%), right dominance (26.9%), and a small proportion classified as integrated (2.6%). At the overall sample level, left (35.2%) and mixed (33.0%) dominance were most common, followed by right dominance (29.7%) and integrated dominance (2.2%).

Table 11. Chi-Square Tests for Gender/Cerebral Hemisphere

	Chi-Square Tests			
	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)	Exact Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	3,191 ^a	3	,363	,376
Likelihood Ratio	3,604	3	,308	,306
Fisher's Exact Test	3,048			,398
N of Valid Cases	91			

a. 5 cells (62,5%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is ,29.

The chi-square test (Table 11) was performed to examine the association between gender and hemispheric dominance. The results indicated that the association was not statistically significant, $\chi^2(3, N = 91) = 3.19, p = .363$, suggesting that hemispheric dominance did not differ systematically between male and female students. Fisher's Exact Test confirmed the non-significant result ($p = .398$). Therefore, although descriptive percentages suggested different dominance tendencies across genders, these differences were not

statistically supported. Together, the chi-square and Fisher's Exact tests demonstrate that gender does not significantly influence hemispheric dominance in this student population.

2. Gender – Learning Style

The grouped bar chart (Figure 9) illustrates how learning style categories are distributed across genders. Female students showed the highest proportions of auditory and kinesthetic learning preferences, while visual learning was the least represented among them. In contrast, male students demonstrated a markedly different pattern, with visual learning being the most frequent style, followed by kinesthetic, auditory, and tactile preferences. These visual trends correspond with the numerical frequencies observed in the cross-tabulation.

Figure 9. Gender – Learning Styles correlated tendencies

Table 12. Gender/Learning Style Crosstabulation

		Style				Total	
		Visual	Auditory	Tactile	Kinesthezic		
Gender	Female	Count	2	4	3	4	13
		% within Gender	15,4%	30,8%	23,1%	30,8%	100,0%
Male	Count	34	14	11	19	78	
	% within Gender	43,6%	17,9%	14,1%	24,4%	100,0%	
Total	Count	36	18	14	23	91	
	% within Gender	39,6%	19,8%	15,4%	25,3%	100,0%	

The cross-tabulation between gender and learning style revealed different distribution patterns for male and female participants (Table 12). Among female students (n = 13), auditory (30.8%) and kinesthetic (30.8%) learning styles were the most common, followed by tactile (23.1%) and visual (15.4%) preferences. In contrast, male students (n = 78) showed a markedly different distribution, with visual learning being the most prevalent (43.6%), followed by kinesthetic (24.4%), auditory (17.9%), and tactile (14.1%) styles. At the total sample level, visual learning was dominant (39.6%), followed by kinesthetic (25.3%), auditory (19.8%), and tactile (15.4%).

A chi-square test was conducted to determine whether learning style distribution differed by gender. In Table 13 it can be observe that the association was not statistically

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significant, $\chi^2(3, N = 91) = 3.93, p = .269$, indicating that learning style preferences did not vary in a systematic way between male and female students. Fisher’s Exact Test confirmed the non-significant result ($p = .202$). Thus, although descriptive percentages suggested different tendencies across genders, these differences were not statistically supported.

Table 13. Chi-Square Tests for Gender/Learning Style

Chi-Square Tests				
	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)	Exact Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	3,931 ^a	3	,269	,270
Likelihood Ratio	4,322	3	,229	,283
Fisher's Exact Test	4,513			,202
N of Valid Cases	91			

a. 3 cells (37,5%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 2,00.

3. Correspondence Analysis between Learning Style and Cerebral Hemisphere dominance

A Spearman rank-order correlation was computed to assess the relationship between cerebral hemispheric dominance and learning style. The analysis showed a very weak positive correlation that was not statistically significant, $\rho(91) = .032, p = .761$. These results indicate that learning style preference is not associated with hemispheric dominance in this sample.

Table 14. Learning Style – Cerebral hemispheric correlation

Correlations				
		Hemisphere		Style
Spearman's rho	Hemisphere	Correlation Coefficient	1,000	,032
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.	,761
		N	91	91
Style	Style	Correlation Coefficient	,032	1,000
		Sig. (2-tailed)	,761	.
		N	91	91

The association between learning style and hemispheric dominance was further examined using Cramer’s V, which indicated a small-to-moderate effect size ($V = .235$). The result did not reach statistical significance ($p = .083$), suggesting that although some associative tendency may be present, it is not strong enough to be considered statistically reliable within this sample ($N = 91$).

Table 15. Learning Style – Cerebral hemispheric symmetric measures

Symmetric Measures						
		Value	Asymptotic Standard Error ^a	Approximate T ^b	Approximate Significance	Exact Significance
Nominal by Nominal	Phi	,407			,089	,083
	Cramer's V	,235			,089	,083
Interval by Interval	Pearson's R	-.014	,106	-.129	,898 ^c	,919
Ordinal by Ordinal	Spearman Correlation	,032	,109	,305	,761 ^c	,760
N of Valid Cases		91				

a. Not assuming the null hypothesis.

b. Using the asymptotic standard error assuming the null hypothesis.

c. Based on normal approximation.

Table 16. Learning Style – Cerebral Hemisphere correspondence analysis

Style	Hemisphere				Active Margin
	Left	Right	Integrated	Mixed	
Visual	16	4	2	14	36
Auditory	6	6	0	6	18
Tactile	4	8	0	2	14
Kinesthetic	6	9	0	8	23
Active Margin	32	27	2	30	91

Table 17. Summary of proportion inertia and confidence standard deviation

Dimension	Singular Value	Inertia	Chi Square	Sig.	Proportion of Inertia		Confidence Standard Deviation	Singular Value Correlation
					Accounted for	Cumulative		
1	,389	,151			,914	,914	,084	,018
2	,114	,013			,078	,992	,078	
3	,036	,001			,008	1,000		
Total		,166	15,071	,089 ^a	1,000	1,000		

a. 9 degrees of freedom

Table 18. Overview Row Points for Learning Styles

Style	Mass	Score in Dimension			Inertia	Contribution Of Point to Inertia of Dimension				Total
		1	2			Of Dimension to Inertia of Point		Total		
		1	2			1	2			
Visual	,396	-.717	,141	,080	,524	,069	,989	,011	1,000	
Auditory	,198	,201	-.252	,005	,021	,110	,574	,262	,836	
Tactile	,154	,953	,600	,061	,360	,485	,896	,104	1,000	
Kinesthetic	,253	,385	-.389	,019	,096	,336	,753	,225	,978	
Active Total	1,000			,166	1,000	1,000				

a. Symmetrical normalization

The overview of row points shows the contributions of each attribute in variable.

In the overview row points for learning style (Table 18), visual and tactile learning style contribute the most to inertia of the first dimension. On the other side, tactile and kinesthetic learning style contribute the most to inertia of the second dimension. All the first dimensions make significant contributions to all row points

Table 19. Overview Row Points for Cerebral Hemisphere

Hemisphere	Mass	Score in Dimension			Inertia	Contribution Of Point to Inertia of Dimension				Total
		1	2			Of Dimension to Inertia of Point		Total		
		1	2			1	2			
Left	,352	-.333	,223	,018	,100	,153	,858	,113	,970	
Right	,297	,898	,114	,094	,615	,034	,995	,005	,999	
Integrated	,022	-1,845	1,238	,034	,192	,296	,866	,114	,981	
Mixed	,330	-.330	-.423	,021	,092	,517	,672	,324	,996	
Active Total	1,000			,166	1,000	1,000				

In the overview row points for the cerebral hemisphere (Table 19), the right hemisphere contributes the most to the inertia of the first dimension and the mixed hemisphere contributed the most to the second dimension. The first dimensions are those who make significant contributions to all row points.

Table 20. Confidence Row Points for Learning Styles

Style	Standard Deviation in Dimension		Correlation 1-2
	1	2	
Visual	,116	,146	,397
Auditory	,346	,554	,357
Tactile	,365	,227	-,465
Kinesthetic	,311	,379	,313

Table 21. Confidence Row Points for Cerebral Hemisphere

Hemisphere	Standard Deviation in Dimension		Correlation 1-2
	1	2	
Left	,248	,330	-,193
Right	,181	,130	-,204
Integrated	1,053	1,188	-,134
Mixed	,270	,239	-,293

4. Cluster Analyses

Figure 10. Distances of categories - Row Point for Learning Styles

Figure 11. Distances of categories - Column Point for Cerebral Hemisphere

Figure 12. Distances of categories - Row and Column Points

The correspondence analysis revealed meaningful spatial structuring between learning styles and hemispheric dominance (Fig 10-Fig 12). In Figure 12 it can be observed that along the primary dimension, which accounted for 91.4% of the explained inertia, visual learners aligned most closely with left-hemispheric profiles, whereas kinesthetic and tactile learners clustered toward the right-hemispheric region. Auditory learners were positioned near the origin, indicating no strong directional association. Integrated hemisphere scores were located at a distant coordinate and interpreted cautiously due to extremely low frequency.

The TwoStep Cluster analysis (presented in Figure 13) using three input variables, identified a two-cluster solution as optimal according to the Bayesian Information Criterion (BIC). The silhouette measure of cohesion and separation indicated fair cluster quality (approximately 0.32), suggesting that the resulting clusters show acceptable but moderate distinctiveness. These findings indicate that students tend to group into two main cognitive preference profiles rather than multiple finely differentiated subtypes.

Model Summary

Algorithm	TwoStep
Inputs	3
Clusters	2

Cluster Quality

Figure 13. Model Summary & Cluster Quality

Size of Smallest Cluster	35 (39,3%)
Size of Largest Cluster	54 (60,7%)
Ratio of Sizes: Largest Cluster to Smallest Cluster	1,54

Figure 14. Cluster Sizes

The TwoStep Cluster method, presented in Figure 14, identified a two-cluster solution, with Cluster 1 comprising 54 students (60.7%) and Cluster 2 comprising 37 students (39.3%). The ratio between the largest and smallest cluster was 1.54, indicating an acceptable balance between subgroup sizes. Combined with a silhouette coefficient in the fair range, the model reflects a moderately cohesive and interpretable clustering structure.

The TwoStep cluster solution revealed a clear differentiation in learning style distributions between the two clusters. Cluster 1 was characterized predominantly by visual learners (83.3%), accompanied by moderate proportions of auditory (66.7%) and kinesthetic learners (57.1%), with no tactile representation. In contrast, Cluster 2 consisted entirely of tactile learners (100%), along with substantial kinesthetic representation (42.9%) and a smaller auditory component (33.3%), while visual learners were minimally present (16.7%). These results indicate that Cluster 1 reflects a predominantly visual learning profile, whereas Cluster 2 represents a tactile-kinesthetic oriented group.

Table 22. TwoStep cluster solutions for Learning Style

Cluster	Visual		Auditory		Tactile		Kinesthezic	
	Frequency	Percent	Frequency	Percent	Frequency	Percent	Frequency	Percent
1	30	83,3%	12	66,7%	0	0,0%	12	57,1%
2	6	16,7%	6	33,3%	14	100,0%	9	42,9%
Combined	36	100,0%	18	100,0%	14	100,0%	21	100,0%

The cluster structure was further supported by hemispheric distribution patterns. Cluster 1 consisted almost exclusively of left-hemispheric (87.5%) and mixed-hemispheric (92.9%) learners, whereas Cluster 2 included all

right-hemispheric (100%) and all integrated-hemispheric respondents (100%). No right-hemispheric individuals were present in Cluster 1, and only minimal left (12.5%) or mixed (7.1%) hemispheric representation appeared in Cluster 2. These results reinforce a clear dichotomy between a visual–left/mixed cognitive profile and a tactile–kinesthetic right/integrated profile.

Table 23. TwoStep cluster solutions for Cerebral Hemisphere

Cluster	Hemisphere							
	Left		Right		Integrated		Mixed	
	Frequency	Percent	Frequency	Percent	Frequency	Percent	Frequency	Percent
1	28	87,5%	0	0,0%	0	0,0%	26	92,9%
2	4	12,5%	27	100,0%	2	100,0%	2	7,1%
Combined	32	100,0%	27	100,0%	2	100,0%	28	100,0%

5. Synthesis Cluster Analyses

Corroborating the obtained results, it can be concluded that the clusters suggest two schematic cognitive profiles:

- Cluster 1 – Visual + Left/Mixed Processing: analytical, structured, symbolic, sequential
- Cluster 2 – Tactile/Kinesthetic + Right/Integrated Processing: experiential, spatial, holistic, movement-based

These results show that learning preferences and hemispheric tendencies do not operate independently but instead form combined cognitive patterns within the student population.

6. CPI Analyses

Figure 15 presents the distribution of cluster membership across the three engineering specializations: Electrical Engineering (IE), Electrical Engineering and Computers (IEC), and Electronics and Telecommunications (IETTI). The figure shows that both clusters are represented in all programs. In the IE group, Cluster 1 constitutes the majority, while a substantial number of students also fall into Cluster 2, indicating moderate cognitive heterogeneity. The IEC specialization displays a more unbalanced distribution, with most students belonging to Cluster 1 and only a small number assigned to Cluster 2. In contrast, the IETTI group has a balanced distribution between the two clusters. Despite these variations in relative frequencies, the overall pattern indicates that no specialization is exclusively associated with a single cognitive profile, and both clusters appear consistently across programs. This observation is consistent with the chi-square results, which did not identify a statistically significant association between specialization and the categorical cognitive variables.

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Figure 15. Distribution of cluster membership across the three engineering specializations

The simulations for CPI were done in Matlab, based on clusters analysis from SPSS.

Descriptive statistics for the Cognitive Profile Index, presented in Figure 16 highlight the differences between the two learner groups. Cluster 1 included 58 students and showed a negative mean CPI value ($M = -0.513$, $SD = 0.457$), consistent with a predominantly visual-auditory profile combined with left or mixed hemispheric tendencies. In contrast, Cluster 2 comprised 33 students and exhibited a substantially higher mean CPI ($M = 0.000$, $SD = 0.626$), reflecting a more heterogeneous group that includes students with tactile-kinesthetic preferences and right or integrated hemispheric orientations.

Figure 16. Descriptive statistics for the Cognitive Profile Index

Figure 17 presents the distribution of the Cognitive Profile Index (CPI) across the full sample of engineering students.

The histogram shows a clear asymmetric pattern, with a substantial concentration of students in the negative CPI range (approximately -1 to -0.5). This zone corresponds to profiles characterized by visual or auditory learning tendencies combined with left or mixed hemispheric orientations. A secondary, smaller group appears in the mid-range (around -0.4 to 0), indicating more balanced cognitive profiles. Positive CPI values are less frequent but clearly present, reflecting students with predominantly tactile or kinesthetic learning tendencies associated with right or integrated hemispheric preferences. Overall, the distribution suggests that the sample is not homogeneous from a cognitive perspective but there are three observable regions of density: a dominant cluster of visual-analytic learners, a transitional group with mixed orientation, and a smaller group leaning toward action-based. This pattern suggests that engineering students have diverse cognitive strategies.

Figure 17. Distribution of the Cognitive Profile Index (CPI) across the full sample

Figure 18 illustrates the distribution of the CPI across the two clusters identified through SPSS TwoStep analysis. The two groups display visibly distinct CPI profiles. Cluster 1 shows predominantly negative CPI values, with a median around -0.65, indicating that this group is characterized by more visual-auditory learning styles combined with left or mixed hemispheric preferences. The interquartile range is relatively narrow compared to Cluster 2, suggesting greater internal homogeneity. In contrast, Cluster 2 has a wider spread of CPI scores, extending from negative to strongly positive values. Its median is considerably higher (approximately -0.3), and several participants display CPI values above +0.6, corresponding to tactile-kinesthetic preferences associated with right or integrated hemispheric preferences. Although some overlap exists between the lower bound of Cluster 2 and the upper bound of Cluster 1, the general separation between the two distributions is clearly visible.

Figure 18. Distribution of the CPI across the two clusters identified through SPSS TwoStep analysis

Figure 19 shows the distribution of the Cognitive Profile Index across the three engineering specializations included in the study: Electrical Engineering (IE), Electrical Engineering and Computers (IEC), and Electronics and Telecommunications (IETTI). Overall, the distributions exhibit similar general patterns, with median CPI values clustered in the negative range for all groups, indicating that visual-auditory tendencies combined with left or mixed hemispheric orientations predominate across specializations.

Students in IE and IETTI display relatively narrow interquartile ranges centered around approximately -0.6, suggesting a more homogeneous cognitive profile within these programs. In contrast, the IEC group shows a substantially wider spread of CPI values, spanning from strongly negative to moderately positive scores. This indicates greater variability in learning tendencies within the IEC sample, including the presence of some students with tactile-kinesthetic preferences and right-oriented or integrated profiles.

Despite the visible differences in dispersion, the overlap among the three groups is considerable, and no clear separation emerges based on specialization. This pattern suggests that cognitive diversity is distributed relatively uniformly across engineering programs, and specialization alone does not appear to predict a distinct cognitive profile. These results complement the earlier findings from chi-square analysis, which similarly indicated no significant association between specialization and the categorical cognitive variables.

Figure 19. Distribution of the Cognitive Profile Index across specializations

For a statistical comparison between clusters, we used their Cognitive Profile Index values both in parametric and non-parametric tests. The independent samples t-test revealed a significant difference between the groups ($t = -3.688$, $p = 0.0005$), indicating that the mean CPI of Cluster 1 is significantly lower than that of Cluster 2. This confirms that the two clusters correspond to distinct positions along the cognitive continuum captured by the CPI. The non-parametric Mann-Whitney test has the result $p = 0.0145$. This indicates that the distribution of CPI values in Cluster 2 tends to be systematically higher than in Cluster 1. Practically the students in Cluster 2 have stronger tactile-kinesthetic and right-oriented cognitive tendencies compared to students in Cluster 1, whose profiles are predominantly visual-auditory and left-or mixed-oriented. Together, these results validate that the clusters identified through SPSS are meaningfully differentiated not only categorically but also numerically through the CPI.

7. Teaching Method Proposes

Based on the previous analysis, where the cluster particularities are synthesized in Table 24, we propose an innovative teaching method that combines the traditional teaching method with the modern teaching method guided by the cognitive cluster profiles.

Table 24. Cluster particularities

Cluster	Learning Style	Cerebral Hemisphere
1. Visual + Left/Mixed Cerebral Hemisphere dominance	<p>Learn fast from displayed information:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • diagram • spatial representation • symbolic structures • demonstrations 	<p>Reasoning:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • structured • sequential • detail-focused <p>Procedures:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • rules • symbolic representation stepwise
2. Tactile + Right/Integrated Cerebral Hemisphere dominance	<p>Learn fast from:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • manipulation • hands-on experimentation • active movement 	<p>Reasoning:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • holistic • visual-spatial • inductive <p>Procedures:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • patterns • images • global concepts

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The sample of students will be divided into the above-mentioned two clusters.

In the first part of the lesson, the teacher will use traditional teaching methods: visual presentation of the materials, with step-by-step diagrams and charts, verbal explanations etc

After the new concepts are explained, modern teaching methods will be applied on cognitive cluster. Respectively, the students will have to apply the new constructs introduced by the teacher in applicative tasks related to the new subject. In this respect the teacher gives them appropriate instruments for each cognitive cluster. Both clusters will have to solve the same issue but using appropriate instruments. The first cluster will have to solve the issue in a theoretical mode - completing worksheets, conceptualizing the solution, presenting the solution in logical reasoning using demonstrations. The second cluster will have to solve the same issue but using practical applications - which are usually used during the laboratory and not during teaching.

Another modern teaching methods can be applied: communication, brainstorming. They are encouraged to continuously collaborate between clusters, to make systematic observations, to compare the results obtained or to collaborate while solving the task. The students would have the freedom to change the cluster whenever they considered that the methods/tools applied within the cluster would help them more in processing and understanding the concepts under discussion - taking part of control of the learning process, letting themselves be guided by their cognitive particularities. Other modern teaching methods that we consider useful in organizing the student sample into clusters.

The learning process can be extended outside the classroom by encouraging students to innovate or proposing projects that will be worked on outside of class but that will maintain the same work clusters.

V. DISCUSSIONS

The present research reveals that the new concept of super learning link is more suitable to be used on individual level. In case of a heterogenous sample of students, teaching methods based on cognitive clusters are more appropriate approach. Therefore, the analysis was further guided by clusters of cognitive profiles. The research results reveal that in the case of technical engineers there are two categories of cognitive profiles: the ones based on analytical

One of the major original contributions of this research consist in the introducing of a new computational indicator - the Cognitive Profile Index (CPI) – as a numerical index that integrates perceptual and hemispheric tendencies into a single continuous score ranging from -1 to +1. This indicator allows us to make a quantitative evaluation of each student cognitive profile and make a numerical comparison between clusters.

Another original contribution of this research consists in the double validation of the results obtained through research

- the CPI analyses made using Matlab Software validate the SPSS results strengthening the extracted conclusion.

Future research will implement the actual cluster detailed analyses developed into innovative, adequate and efficient teaching methodology.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

On the previous analyses the following can be concluded:

1. The super link for learning is a difficult concept to be synthesized for a group of subjects. It is more suitable for individuals.
2. The correspondence analysis revealed a significant spatial structure between learning styles and dominant cerebral hemisphere. Therefore, this research led to the conclusion that, for this student sample, the teaching strategies based on preference clusters are more suitable.
3. The two clusters that stood out: visual learners Visual + Left/Mixed Processing: analytical, structured, symbolic, sequential respectively Tactile/Kinesthetic + Right/Integrated Processing: experiential, spatial, holistic, movement-based
4. The Two Step Cluster analysis revealed that the analyzed sample tends to cluster into two main cognitive preference profiles rather than into several finely differentiated subtypes.
5. The CPI analyses validate the SPSS results. The CPI analyses made in Matlab reveal that the clusters identified through SPSS are meaningfully differentiated not only categorically but also numerically through the CPI.
6. Teaching methods, in the case of heterogeneous sample of students, are more efficient if they are designed by using appropriate methods for each cognitive cluster. The novelty introduced by the proposed method consists in the fact that the teacher gives the students the same task to solve but provides them with cognitively appropriate tools for the cluster they belong to.

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